

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF THE NEXT GENERATION LUNAR RETROREFLECTOR ON THE MOON IN MARE CRISIUM. D. G. Currie.¹, D. Baden¹, D. D. Wellnitz¹, C. S. Wu¹, G. O. Delle Monache², B. B. Behr¹, J. G. Williams³, D. H. Boggs³, W. Kleyman¹, L. Wise¹, R. C. Carter¹, N. Russo,¹, S. Dell’Agnello², C. C. Davis, P. S. Russ¹, L. Putnam¹, M. Peckerar¹, C. Courde⁴, J.Eckl⁵, and N.Colmenares⁶
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Introduction: On the 3rd and the 4th of March 2025, the Lunar Laser Ranging Observatories (LLROs) in Grasse, France and Wettzell, Germany and later the APOLLO LLRO obtained thousands of successful individual range measurements, collected into more than thirty normal point intervals, to our Next Generation Lunar Reflector (NGLR-1) on the Moon in Mare Crisium. The launch was performed by SpaceX’s Falcon 9 rocket at 1:11 am on the 15th of January from the Kennedy Space Center. NGLR-1 was carried to the Moon by Firefly Aerospace’s Blue Ghost lander. The Blue Ghost successfully deployed NGLR-1 on the Moon on the 2nd of March at which time the LLROs began Lunar Laser Ranging (LLR) operations to search for laser returns from NGLR-1 on the Moon.

Figure 1 NGLR-1 as delivered to Firefly Aerospace for mounting on the Blue Ghost lander.

NGLR Project Objectives: The individual range measurements to the existing retroreflector arrays on the Moon suffer from an intrinsic uncertainty due to the combination of multiple Cube Corner Retroreflectors and the libration of the Moon. This leads to an unavoidable changing uncertainty, or dispersion in the values of the individual range measurement. This the magnitude of this dispersion then depends upon the phase of the Moon. The magnitude of the Normal point Value (NPV) depends upon the inverse of the magnitude of the dispersion. The NGLR Project consists of creating a Retroreflector package with a single large CCR. This will eliminate the contribution to the ranging dispersion contributed by the retroreflector on the Moon. The value of the

dispersion will then be determined by the hardware configuration of the LLRO [1].

NGLR-1 Configuration: The core of NGLR-1 is this single solid retroreflector, the CCR. The retention of a strong return signal depends upon the minimization of internal thermal gradient in the CCR. The essential specular reflection of the rear three mirror is protected by the RCH. The forward vulnerability of the three rear reflecting mirrors is protected by centimetres of fused silica. To protect of the CCR from the solar radiation and the thermal emission of the hot regolith, the Rear Conformal Housing (RCH) enclosed the back of the CCR. To reduce the thermal emission from the hot RCH the inside is coated with Laser Gold, which has an extremely low emissivity, between 1% and 0.4% in the expected temperature range. The CCR is supported by the Front Ring Housing (FRH) through the tabs on the CCR. The tabs are supported by Teflon Rings to survive the shock of launch and separation and Thermal Resistance Rings to reduce the heat flow from the hot FRH to the CCR via the tabs. A support structure than interfaces between the FRH and the Antennae support panel of the Blue Ghost Lander.

NGLR-1 Performance: The three primary objectives of NGLR-1 are a very small dispersion, the Rate of Return (RoR) of the laser pulse equal to the RoR of the Apollo 11 retroreflector array and, finally, a very long lifetime.

Demonstration of low dispersion. On the 4th of March, two days after NGLR-1 was deployed, the LLRO in Wettzell Germany obtained returns and demonstrated a dispersion limited only by the hardware confirmation at the Wettzell LLRO.

Demonstration of a RoR like the Apollo 11 Array. On March 3rd, the second day after the NGLR-1 was deployed, the LLRO in Grasse, France obtained 1,239 Individual Range Measurements (IRMs) to NGLR-1 and 2,146 IRMs to NGLR-1 on 4 March combined into 36 NPIs. The objective of our NGLR project has been to achieve a Cross-Section (C-S) approximately equal to the C-S of the Apollo 11 retroreflector array. The preliminary range measurement data from the Grasse LLRO has been analysed to determine the C-S of NGLR-1 as compared to the C-S of the Apollo 11 retroreflector array (A11). The C-S of NGLR-1 is 100% +/- 18% of the C-S of A11 when calibrated with the C-S of A15/3.

Further, the C-S of NGLR-1 is 65%+/- 17% of the C-S of A11 when calibrated with the average of the C-Ss of A11&A14. Further, the LLROs are currently transmitting linear polarization with an undetermined orientation angle rather than the design polarization of the NGLR-1. The C-S should be significantly improved when the LLROs complete the installation of the hardware for the control of the angle of polarization.

Projected NGLR-1 Very Long Lifetime: The accuracy of the science results is, in general, linearly depend upon the time span of the input data. For example, it took ~30 years of data to discovery the liquid core of the Moon. While we obviously cannot demonstrate the long lifetime at this time, the design of NGLR-1 has employed demonstrated aspects to address the lifetime in the presence of solar wind, solar UV radiation and micrometeorites (dust). The high degree of specular reflection of the three rear mirrors is protected by the RCH. The forward surface of the three rear mirrors is protected by centimetres of fused silica. This is the same approach that was used on the Apo011o 11 retroreflector array that is still operational after 57 years. We expect dust to be deposited on the front surface, as has been the case with the Apollo 11 array, but the advances in laser performance has far exceeded the rate of dust deposition.

Projected Science Results of the NGLR/LLR project:

The objective of the NGLR-1 project, and of the later deployments of NGLR-2 and NGLR-3, is to greatly improve the precision (the standard deviation of the magnitude of the residuals) and thus the accuracy of the LLR measurements. The analysis of preliminary data obtained during the first month of operation indicate the ranging precision and the relative local accuracy objectives have been achieved. These objectives and analysis of the early results obtained during the initial test phase [1] will be discussed.

The improved precision in LLR provided by the NGLR-1 provides two effective advantages with respect to ranging to the retroreflector arrays. The uncertainty of the average magnitudes of the residuals in a Normal Point Interval (NPI) depends upon the square root of the precision. This means that NGLR-1 will improve the precision of the magnitude of the average of the returns in an NPI to a factor up to four with respect to the precision for the same number of returns from the Apollo 15 retroreflector array. The second advantage is the reduction of the impact of the noise from the sun-lit Moon and/or the sun-lit Earth's atmosphere. This advantage depends linearly on the dispersion, so the ranging to the NGLR-1 can improve the detectability of returns by a factor up to 17 with respect to the detectability for the Apollo 15 array.

In order to determine the accuracy of science results that may be expected due to the improved precision, simulations of a 6-year mission addressing the expected improvement in the accuracy of the scientific results were performed with Jim Williams of JPL [2]. This analysis indicates that the scientific results, beginning when all three NGLRs are deployed, may be expected to provide an order of magnitude improvement in the accuracy of the various scientific results as compared to the current scientific accuracy that has been obtained using the Apollo Retroreflector Arrays (ARAs) and the Lunokhod retroreflector arrays. The analysis using the latter has already discovered the liquid core of the Moon, obtained the best estimate of any possible deviations of the Weak Equivalence Principle, provided the best evaluation of the temporal and spatial changes in Big G, and provided many of the best tests of General Relativity.

Case	Beta	Gamma	h^2	l^2	cos D	$\langle a \rangle$	Tau S 815 d
SPL	92%	74%	87%	70%	98%	98%	7%
	13x	3.9x	7.9x	3.3x	56x	50x	40x
CRS WST	99%	99.8%	99.5%	99.8%	99.4%	99.3%	99.7%
SW SPL	111x	420x	212x	570x	162x	147x	330x

Table 2 Factors and percentages of improvement with the Artemis III mission and the assumption that ranging by the LLROs is performed at the ultimate levels of accuracy supported by the basic SBR package.

A brief review of the operational issues and design history of NGLR-1 [3,4] will be compared to our Apollo 11 Retroreflector Array.

References: [1] The Objectives NGLR-1 Project <https://www.physics.umd.edu/nglr/> [2] Williams J. G. Boggs D. H. Currie D. G. (2022) Next-generation laser ranging at lunar geophysical network and commercial lander payload service sites The Planetary Science Journal 3 (6), 136-150 [2] Currie D. G. Dell'Agnello S. Delle Monache G. O. (2013) A lunar laser ranging retroreflector array for the 21st century Acta Astronautica 68 (7-8), 667-680. [4] A general description of the NGLR Project <https://www.physics.umd.edu/nglr/> [5] Description of the SOOTO Suite of Simulation programs <https://www.physics.umd.edu/nglr/>

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